

Aromatic Disulphides and Sugden's Parachors. Part IV.

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Sulphur exhibits valencies of one, two, three, four and six in combination with other elements. With another sulphur atom it forms a strong link and in consequence, long chains of sulphur atoms are readily formed. Lecher (*Ber.*, 1915, 48, 524 and subsequent papers) has shown that diphenyldisulphide, di-*p*-dimethylaminodiphenyldisulphide, di-*o*-nitrophenyldisulphide and *o*-nitrodiphenyldisulphide exhibit thermochromic properties. This change in colour might be due to dissociation into free radicals, as, such dissociation has been observed in the case of nitrogen (in tetra-aryl hydrazines, Wieland, *Annalen*, 1912, 392, 156) and oxygen (in some aromatic peroxides, Pummerer and Cherbuliez, *Ber.*, 1914, 47, 2957).

Lecher (*Ber.*, 1925, 58, 417) attempted to apply to compounds of sulphur those methods (such as replacement of the group R in the compound $RX \cdot XR$ by the group RX), which have been shown to promote dissociation into radicals in the cases of compounds of nitrogen and carbon, but he failed to get any evidence of the existence of radicals with univalent sulphur. He, therefore, concluded that the colour changes are due not to dissociation into free radicals or to rearrangement of the atoms, but to a redistribution of the valencies.

In this investigation some of the aromatic disulphides have been studied in the fused state by the method of parachor determination. The parachor method has been extensively employed by Sugden (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 127, 1525 and subsequent papers); see also Bhatnagar and others (*J. Chim. phys.*, 1928, 25, 21; *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 6, 269).

EXPERIMENTAL.

- I. 1. Diphenyldisulphide, m.p. 66.5°.
2. 4:4'-Dichlorodiphenyldisulphide, m.p. 71.5°.
3. 4:4'-Dibromodiphenyldisulphide, m.p. 93.8°.

4. 4:4'-Dimethyldiphenyldisulphide, m.p. 46.0°.
 5. 4:4'-Dimethoxydi-*m*-tolylidysulphide, m.p. 73.5°.
 6. $\beta\beta'$ -Dinaphthyldisulphide, m.p. 199.0° (prepared by the method of Stewart, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, 121, 2555).

- II. 1. Dibenzylidysulphide, m.p. 71.0°.
 2. 2:2'-Dinitrodibenzylidysulphide, m.p. 112.0° (obtained by the method of Price and Twiss, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1909, 98, 1490).

Density was determined with a U-shaped pycnometer (Sugden, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 126, 1171) and surface tension by the method of maximum bubble pressure with an apparatus previously described by the authors (*loc. cit.*). The results are given in Table I.

TABLE I.

Substance.	Temperature.	Density. g./c.c.	Surface tension dynes/cm.	Parachor, Fobs.
1. Diphenyldisulphide	64.9°	1.155	40.58	476.8
	79.1°	1.142	39.08	477.6
	96.8°	1.127	37.29	478.5
	118.0°	1.110	35.08	478.5
			Mean	477.9
2. 4:4'-Dichlorodiphenyl- disulphide.	76.2°	1.328	41.90	550.1
	88.1°	1.317	40.55	550.1
	109.3°	1.304	39.39	550.7
			Mean	550.6
3. 4:4'-Dibromodiphenyl- disulphide.	99.0°	1.664	41.90	575.0
	115.0°	1.647	40.89	575.3
	136.0°	1.626	38.51	576.1
	152.0°	1.610	37.24	577.1
			Mean	575.9
4. 4:4'-Dimethyldiphenyl- disulphide.	51.2°	1.114	39.00	553.5
	69.3°	1.100	37.30	553.1
	89.2°	1.084	35.00	552.5
	111.0°	1.068	33.13	553.8
			Mean	559.4

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Substance.	Temperature.	Density. g./c.c.	Surface tension dynes/cm.	Parachor, Pobs.
5. 4:4'-Dimethoxydi- <i>m</i> -tolyl- disulphide.	76.8°	1.160	40.15	664.6
	89.7°	1.149	38.86	665.5
	100.5°	1.139	37.84	666.8
	117.0°	1.128	36.28	667.4
				Mean
6. <i>ββ'</i> -Dinaphthyl- disulphide.	144.0°	1.144	37.20	687.1
	155.0°	1.138	36.98	689.5
	169.0°	1.128	36.24	692.1
				Mean
7. Dibenzyl- disulphide.	75.2°	1.105	38.73	555.9
	88.0°	1.094	37.43	556.7
	100.2°	1.085	36.42	557.5
	112.5°	1.075	35.26	559.1
				Mean
8. 2:2'-Dinitrodibenzyl- disulphide.	115.0°	1.208	44.81	665.3
	125.0°	1.298	43.53	665.3
	140.0°	1.285	42.25	666.5
				Mean

Discussion.

If an element possesses n valency electrons, then its normal valency is n or $8-n$, whichever is the smaller. Higher valencies may be ascribed to—(1) the transference of electrons from one atom to another as in polar bonds and in semi-polar double bonds, (2) the sharing of more than the normal number of electrons and (3) the formation of singlet linkages.

An atom of sulphur possesses six valency electrons and on the above hypothesis its normal valency is two. In aromatic disulphides the sulphur atom may be divalent and might exert a higher valency of four or six, by sharing more than the normal number of electrons

with the second sulphur atom in the molecule. An aromatic disulphide, thus, may have any of the structures given below:—

In every case the shell of eight electrons around each sulphur atom is not exceeded.

Assuming the above structures for the disulphides, their parachors are calculated from the constants of Sugden (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 125, 1180 and subsequent papers). The parachor for naphthalene ring has been taken from a previous paper of the authors (*loc. cit.*). The parachors $P_{\text{calc.}}$ so obtained in each case are compared with the parachors $P_{\text{obs.}}$ obtained from the surface tension data in Table II.

TABLE II.

Substance.	$P_{\text{obs.}}$	P			
		Structure I.	Structure II.	Structure III.	Structure IV.
1. Diphenyldisulphide ...	477.9	476.4	499.6	522.8	569.2
2. 4:4'-Dichlorodiphenyldisulphide ...	550.6	550.8	574.0	597.2	643.6
3. 4:4'-Dibromodiphenyldisulphide ...	575.9	578.2	601.4	624.6	671.0
4. 4:4'-Dimethyldiphenyldisulphide ...	552.9	554.4	577.6	600.8	647.2
5. 4:4'-Dimethoxydi- <i>m</i> -tolylidysulphide ...	666.1	672.4	695.6	719.8	765.2
6. <i>pp'</i> -Dinaphthylidysulphide ...	689.6	689.2	711.4	734.6	791.0
7. Dibenzylidysulphide ...	557.1	554.4	577.6	600.8	647.2
8. 2:2'-Dinitrodibenzylidysulphide ...	665.7	668.6	691.8	715.0	761.4

From the above table it is evident that the parachors $P_{\text{calc.}}$ calculated according to the structure (I) are in good agreement with the observed parachors, except in case of 4:4'-dimethoxydi-*m*-tolylidysulphide where the values differ by 6.3 units. This appears to be due to association. The associated liquids, *viz.*, alcohols, phenols and fatty acids, etc., give parachors 4-8 units lower than the calculated

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(Sugden, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 126, 1185; Jones, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, p. 1196; and Hunter and Maass, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 51, 161). Since 4:4'-dimethoxydi-*m*-tolylidysulphide contains two substituted hydroxy groups, namely, two methoxy groups, it should behave similarly in the fused state and the low value of its parachor is thus accounted for.

These large parachor differences in the other cases cannot be explained on any abnormal behaviour, which the aromatic disulphides might exhibit in the fused state. Sulphur is neither quadrivalent nor hexavalent but is found to be bivalent in the disulphides in the fused state.

An aromatic disulphide is thus represented by the structure (I).

Each sulphur atom in the molecule forms two normal covalencies to complete its octet. Of these eight electrons, one pair is shared with a carbon atom of the aromatic group and another pair is shared with the second sulphur in the molecule; while the other four are not shared and form two "lone" pairs around each sulphur atom.

Although each sulphur atom in the molecule is in this sense saturated, it can form two more co-ordinate covalencies by sharing these "lone" pairs with atoms, for example of oxygen, which need two electrons to complete their octet. Thus the possibility of co-ordination enables the sulphur atom to increase its covalency from two to four, which explains the formation of an aromatic disulphone from an aromatic disulphide.

Summary.

1. Surface tension and density of diphenyldisulphide, 4:4'-dichlorodiphenyldisulphide, 4:4'-dibromodiphenyldisulphide, 4:4'-dimethyldiphenyldisulphide, 4:4'-dimethoxydi-*m*-tolylidysulphide, $\beta\beta'$ -dinaphthyldisulphide, dibenzylidysulphide, 2:2'-dinitrodibenzylidysulphide have been determined at various temperatures in the fused state.

2. Parachors for these substances in the fused state have been calculated from the observed data as well as from the values of atomic and structural constants.

3. Sulphur exerts its normal valency (*viz.*, two) in these aromatic disulphides in the fused state.

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